

Research Article

Tui Na Massage Increases Appetite in Undernourished Toddlers

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Abstract: Background: Malnutrition is a condition that can occur quickly or for a long time, occurs in toddlers and experiences abnormal growth. The toddler period is the most important stage of development, and toddlers who experience malnutrition will experience decreased appetite and get sick easily. Family efforts to overcome malnutrition apart from choosing healthy and nutritious food, can also do Tui Na massage independently for children under five with malnutrition. Massage Tui Na is a therapy from China that can help improve hormones to increase the effectiveness of circulation in increasing toddlers' appetite. **Purpose:** to see the effectiveness of Tui Na massage in increasing children's appetite to increase body weight. The descriptive research method use case study method through the nursing care process which consists of identifying studies on toddlers and families, measuring anthropometric status, and doing Tui Na massages. **Results:** two family participants with toddlers whose weight did not match their age were given Tui Na massage with the same frequency for 6 consecutive days, one toddler had a positive response, namely experiencing an increase in appetite resulting in weight gain, and one toddler not gaining weight. **Conclusion:** parents have a contribution to make in choosing healthy and nutritious food to increase children's appetite so that their weight is appropriate for their age, and Tui Na massage can be done independently to help increase toddlers' appetite so that toddlers' weight increases.

Keywords: Malnutrition, Tui Na, nutrition, family, massage.

Introduction

Toddlerhood is the most important developmental stage in life, so it can be very important. This is very important because it requires careful attention because it is at this point that the process of growth and development takes place which is very visible such as physical growth, physical development, spiritual as well as social [1]. Toddler who have a high incidence of malnutrition or disturbed growth and development will easily get sick and experience loss of appetite. There are several things that toddler need to achieve optimal growth and development, such as parenting in terms of food intake, affection, as well as parenting in certain abilities. Toddler-aged children often feel lazy to eat, and this usually occurs at the age of 1 year. Often the things that cause a lack of appetite are accompanying eating disorders [2]. Perceptions and knowledge of family health, family culture, environment, food availability also affect nutritional intake and toddler growth.

The Coordinating Minister for Human Development and Culture Muhadjir Effendy explained, several kinds of problems had caused an increase in the number of stunting in the areas visited such as the problem of lack of nutrition for a long time in children, difficulty getting access to water, lack of family knowledge, wrong parenting style, and the inadequacy of health workers such as nutritionists to monitor the growth and development of toddlers [3]. The World Health Organization [4] reports that there is an increase in malnutrition in the world from 17.6% in 2015 to 25.0% in

2020. The 2018 Basic Health Research, the malnutrition rate experienced by toddlers in Indonesia is 3.8%. The percentage of undernourished is 11.4%. This research is almost the same as the Nutritional Status Monitoring (PSG) research with the nutritional value of malnutrition experienced by toddlers, namely 3.5% and malnutrition, which is 11.3% [5]. Prevalence of toddlers with malnutrition in the DKI Jakarta area from 2016 (14.29%), 2017 (14%) and 2018 (14.30%) [6].

Eating disorders in children must be addressed immediately because they have negative effects on the body such as lack of nutrition, lack of fluids, underweight, electrolyte imbalances, slowing in the development of gross and fine motor skills, having excessive anxiety, as well as other potentials that can threaten the child's growth process-kids and toddlers. If this situation is not acted upon quickly, it will lead to more serious complications, such as the occurrence of below average height [7].

The government's efforts to improve nutrition are very important which aim to improve the quality of individual nutrition. Requiring the central and regional governments to develop a food and nutrition action plan (RAPG) every five years [8]. In addition to the government's efforts, the family also has a very important role to play an active role in dealing with malnutrition. The family plays a role in meeting nutritional and food needs in the right way [9]. At the age of 3-5 years, many toddlers only like to consume one type of food. Families sometimes do not monitor the quantity and quality of eating in toddlers. Therefore the role of the family also plays an important role in dealing with nutritional problems that occur in toddlers [10].

The role of the family nurse in health education in the family must be further strengthened, especially in solving early childhood nutrition problems. The role of nurses in the family is very broad because nurses must be able to protect clients from things that can harm clients, such as being a communicator by providing clear and accurate information both orally and in writing, as well as being an advocate who is responsible for the actions given to clients [11].

The role of family nurses in children under five with malnutrition, can provide nursing actions called Massage TUI Na. This therapy is a massage action that is made more specifically to improve appetite in toddlers by increasing blood circulation to the spleen and digestion, using the action of acupuncture without using needles, this action emphasizes the body's meridian points or lines of energy flow, so it is relatively lighter than acupuncture [12].

The results of research conducted by [7] for three days showed that before the TUI Na massage was carried out, as many as 25 toddlers had difficulty eating, after being given the TUI Na massage to toddlers, it showed that 2 toddlers had difficulty eating, then as many as 23 toddlers were not in a difficult condition eat. From the results of research conducted [12], massage therapy given to toddlers with difficulty eating has a good or positive response.

Method

This research uses descriptive research with a case study method. Toddlers with poor appetite, Underweight (weight not according to age), Toddlers aged 3-5 years, Toddlers and cooperative parents, Parents willing to sign informed consent, KMS on the yellow line. Before the action was taken, both participants were given an explanation of the reasons, the purpose of nursing care, especially the application of massage Tui Na. After being given an explanation, both participants were given an informed consent form to be signed as evidence of the participants' willingness.

The application of TUI Na Massage is given to two toddlers aged 3-5 years with malnutrition, carried out once a day for a week (6 days) on a regular basis. This massage is given before or 1 hour after meals or at any time desired. The thing that must be considered is that when doing the massage, the toddler is not currently experiencing pain and at least 2 days after immunization to avoid new problems from residual immunization wounds [13].

Results

Identification of the causes of undernutrition in the family is economic difficulties, the family does not understand nutrition. Low economic level where family income ranges from IDR 1,000,000-IDR 1,500,000 a month to meet the needs of 5 people, and there is a lack of parental education on nutrition. In toddler A there were no infectious diseases, the environment around toddler A was clean and neat. Toddler H causes malnutrition, namely economic level and difficulty in making decisions to provide food if their child has no appetite. The condition of the toddler is healthy, the environment where he lives is not neat because his mother sells.

The two families carried out educational actions in the morning using leaflets and back and forth media, this media is to make it easier for families to understand health problems that occur in toddlers. Tui Na massage is carried out after being given education about nutrition. Before the action is taken, the family is given an example of the Tui Na massage movement via video, this is done to make it easier for the family to carry out this action independently and to give confidence to the family that the action taken will not harm the family, especially for toddlers. This action is carried out using oil to avoid injury to toddlers.

Table 1. Weight Monitoring

S/N	Client	Weight (Assessment)	Day (Weight/kg)					
			1	2	3	4	5	6
1	Client A	9,3	9,3	9,3	9,3	9,3	9,3	9,3
2	Client H	10	10	10	10,1	10,2	10,3	10,5

Toddler A did not experience weight gain due to inhibiting factors, namely the toddler at that time had a cold cough, the family did not do Tui Na massage independently, did not give the toddler the right portion and type of food. Toddler A's family did not do the Tui Na massage independently because they were afraid and busy at work. On the 5th day of the Tui Na massage, Toddler A experienced canker sores so he had no appetite and only spent three mouthfuls of food. Families also do not take advantage of available health care facilities. Toddler H experienced weight gain on the third day. This is because families carry out TUI Na massages independently according to recommendations, and monitor the right types of food for healthy toddlers and toddlers.

Discussion

There was a difference in weight in the two toddlers. Toddler A did not gain weight during the 6 days of the visit, this happened because according to the theory of malnutrition caused by difficult economic conditions and supported by a lack of family knowledge, this was the trigger for the lack of protein and calorie intake needed by toddler A. Economic difficulties greatly affected the family in meeting the food needs of toddlers in accordance with what should be consumed. Lack of knowledge can be seen through toddlers only consuming 3-4 tablespoons, consuming more fast food. And in the process on the fifth and sixth day, toddler A experienced canker sores. Toddler H experienced a weight gain of 0.5 kg before the massage. This is supported by the family, especially the toddler's mother, repeating the Tui Na massage action independently, and when given food, the toddler eats while playing with friends around him. This is in line with research conducted by Meinawati [7] toddlers who were given the Tui Na Massage experienced weight gain. So, TUI Na massage is an effective action in increasing appetite in toddlers so that toddlers experience weight gain.

Conclusion

One of the things that is needed in improving nutrition, starting with family economic factors and the family's ability to fulfill family health duties, is how families make decisions to improve toddler nutrition. The role and support of the family are also the main determining factors in increasing the appetite of toddlers.

Declarations

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